

A Joint Spatiotemporal Differential Expression Modeling of Exposure Effects in Spatial Transcriptomics Data

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Abstract

Differential expression analysis in spatial transcriptomics data is important for identifying localized biological processes and spatially structured gene regulation. While numerous methods have been developed for identifying differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in conventional single-cell RNA-seq data, approaches that explicitly account for spatial and temporal context remain scarce. A major challenge in spatial DEG analysis is the spatial misalignment between tissue sections under control and perturbed conditions, which renders coordinate-based comparisons unreliable. To address this gap, we developed `SpatialDENet`, a framework that identifies DEGs in spatially structured single-cell data by incorporating spatial information through a hierarchical network-based model. This approach accounts for spatial confounding and leverages tissue architecture to align biological signals across conditions. We validated `SpatialDENet` through simulation studies and comparative benchmarks with existing popular methods. Our findings demonstrate that `SpatialDENet` provides a powerful and interpretable alternative for spatial transcriptomics analysis and may inform the development of targeted therapies.

Key Words: Bayesian inference, Network model, Differential expression analysis, Gaussian Markov Random Field, Zero-inflation.

1 Introduction

Spatial transcriptomics technologies are increasingly popular for investigating the spatial architecture of tissues, uncovering cell-cell interactions, and analyzing gene expression patterns in situ with high resolution^{1,2}. However, conducting Differential Expression (DE) analysis to identify differentially expressed genes (DEG) between two biological conditions on spatial transcriptomics data presents significant challenges due to its high dimensionality, noise, sparsity, and spatial structure.

Methods for DE analysis in studying biological variations at the single-cell level are emerging quickly. For instance, the popularly used methods include DESeq2³, EdgeR⁴, Lima⁵, MAST⁶, Zinbwave⁷, among others. However, most of these methods do not account for spatial variation, an important source of biological and technical variability that can confound differential expression analysis results⁸. Existing statistical and computational methods⁸⁻¹³ for analyzing spatially resolved

single-cell data are particularly designed to identify spatially variable genes (SVGs), and no adequate attention has been given to identifying DEGs between control and treatment scenarios in spatially resolved single-cell data.

To address this concern, we proposed a statistical framework, *SpatialDENet* (Spatial Differential Expression Analysis through Network), to identify differential expression genes between control and perturbed conditions while correcting for spatial confounding (SC). *SpatialDENet* addresses three main analytical concerns in spatially resolved single-cell data. Firstly, *SpatialDENet* adjusts for the SC issue through spatial hierarchical modeling. This method allows the accurate estimation of the impact of a specific treatment on cells after controlling for the spatial effects. Secondly, spatially resolved single-cell data is associated with spatial misalignment due to the non-longitudinal and non-homologous nature of the data across samples. That is, the spatial coordinates change from tissue samples to samples. To address this concern, *SpatialDENet* leverages network models to map cellular spatial neighborhoods between multiple tissues unto a latent space, creating a unified spatial field for adjusting for SC and identifying DEGs. Lastly, *SpatialDENet* accounts for the sparsity in the expression data. The zeros due to sparsity can arise from technical limitations in the sequencing process or reflect true biological absences of gene expression for specific cells. Distinguishing between these two sources of zeros is critical for accurate interpretation. *SpatialDENet* utilizes a two-part (count and activation) zero-inflated model to account for excess zeros.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. We first briefly describe the statistical framework of *SpatialDENet* and its extension to accommodate zero-inflated data. We then benchmark the framework with popularly used differential expression analysis methods through a simulation study. Finally, we conclude with a summary of our contributions and potential directions for future research.

2 Statistical Framework

2.1 Background of differential analysis framework

In single-cell DE analysis, the general framework adopted by existing methods can be described as follows. Let Y_{gs} be the observed expression level (e.g., read count) for gene g in cell s , where $g = 1, \dots, G$ and $s = 1, \dots, S$. A generalized linear model (GLM) is typically used to model gene expression as:

$$Y_{gs} \sim \text{NB}(\mu_{gs}, \phi_g), \tag{1}$$

where NB denotes a Negative Binomial distribution, μ_{gs} is the expected expression level of gene g in cell s , ϕ_g is a gene-specific dispersion parameter. The parameter μ_{gs} is then linked to covariates

through a log-linear model given as

$$\log(\mu_{gs}) = \beta_{g0} + \log(l_s) + c_s \beta_{g1} + \mathbf{x}_s^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_g, \quad (2)$$

where l_s is a size factor or library size normalization for cell s , β_0 is the model intercept, $c_s \in \{0, 1\}$ is the treatment indicator, with effect size β_1 , \mathbf{x}_s is a vector of covariates to adjust for observed confounding variables, and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_g$ is a corresponding vector of regression coefficients for gene g .

To test for differentially expressed genes between control and treatment conditions, we define the hypothesis (Hypothesis 1) for a specific gene g as

$$H_0 : \beta_{g1} = 0 \quad \text{vs.} \quad H_1 : \beta_{g1} \neq 0, \quad (3)$$

where β_{g1} is the coefficient corresponding to the condition of interest.

In single-cell spatially resolved data with genes exhibiting spatial variation and zero inflation, Hypothesis 1 becomes problematic and inappropriate for finding differential expression genes in single-cell analysis.

2.2 SpatialDENet: The proposed framework

To address the above concern, we proposed a unified framework that addresses spatial confounding, spatial misalignment, the temporal evolution of gene expression, and zero-inflation problems in single-cell spatially resolved data.

2.2.1 Response model

Consider a scenario where we have pre-processed single-cell expression data collected over time. Let Y_{gst} , $s = 1, 2, \dots, S$; $g = 1, 2, \dots, G$, $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ be a gene expression count at spatial location denoted by s at time t for gene g . S is the total number of spots/cells across all tissues. Note here that the cell index s previously defined as a cell is now redefined as a spot index s in spatial transcriptomics data. We assume that

$$Y_{gst} \mid \beta_{g0}, \beta_{g1}, \boldsymbol{\beta}_g \sim \text{NB}(\mu_{gst}, \phi_g), \quad (4)$$

$$\log(\mu_{gst}) = \beta_{g0} + \log(l_{st}) + c_{st} \beta_{g1} + \mathbf{x}_{st}^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_g + \psi_{gst},$$

where ψ_{gst} is a spatiotemporal latent variation used to adjust for spatial confounding in the gene expression data, l_{st} is the size factor, $c_{st} \in \{0, 1\}$ is the condition indicator of spatial point s at time t . The differential genes are then identified using Hypothesis 1.

In standard spatial statistical modeling, where the spatial location domain remains fixed, ψ_{gst} in Equation (4) can be easily estimated by assuming a Gaussian Markov random field (GMRF) prior distribution. However, in single-cell analysis, the spatial domain (tissue sample) dissociates during data collection and thus, different tissues are used in the treatment and control conditions,

causing spatial misalignment due to non-homologous tissue samples. To address this challenge, we model ψ_{gst} using a Network-Based-GMRF prior distribution, which is discussed in the subsequent subsection.

2.2.2 Deriving network-based-GMRF

To define a network-based Gaussian Markov Random Field (GMRF) prior for modeling spatiotemporal latent effects, we introduce a framework that constructs a dynamic cell-neighborhood network over a spatial domain, informed by gene expression summaries¹⁴.

Let \mathcal{D} denote a regular spatial domain for a specific tissue sample, such that $s \in \mathcal{D}$. For each time t or a specific tissue sample, the domain $\mathcal{D}_t \subset \mathcal{D}$ is non-linearly partitioned into non-overlapping spatial regions $D_{it}, i = 1, 2, \dots, I$, called a node, such that

$$\mathcal{D}_t = \bigcup_{i=1}^{I_t} D_{it}, \quad D_{it} \cap D_{i't} = \emptyset \quad \text{for } i \neq i'. \quad (5)$$

For each partition D_{it} , we calculate a representative centroid using a summary statistic, such as the mean expression of the principal components (PCs) derived from the gene expression data. Suppose the reduced gene expression space consists of 10 PCs; for each partition D_{it} , we compute the mean value of each PC across all cells within that partition. Consequently, each D_{it} is represented by a vector of 10 mean values, corresponding to the 10 PCs. The number of nodes is chosen to result in optimal precision. We then define a cell-neighborhood network \mathcal{T} by connecting each node D_{it} to its k -nearest neighbors based on centroid proximity. Formally, define an undirected graph $\mathcal{T} = (\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{E})$, where \mathcal{G} is the set of nodes (partitions across all t) and \mathcal{E} is the set of edges, such that $(i, t) \sim (j, t')$ if and only if $D_{jt'}$ is among the k nearest neighbors of D_{it} based on centroid distance. For example, if there exists a total of 1000 non-overlapping partitions of \mathcal{D} , the network \mathcal{T} will have 1000 nodes ($\#\mathcal{G} = 1000$), indicating that each cell/spot belongs to only one of the 1000 nodes. Given the nodes in \mathcal{G} , the Network \mathcal{T} is used to incorporate the spot/cell interaction and dependencies informed by the relationship between the cell's expression status across all the genes.

To obtain the network-based GMRF, suppose network \mathcal{T} has n nodes, with $\psi_{git} \in \mathbb{R}$ representing the node latent effect for node i at time t . Let $\boldsymbol{\psi}_{gt} = (\psi_{g1t}, \psi_{g2t}, \dots, \psi_{gnt})^T$ and $\boldsymbol{\psi}_g = (\psi_{g1}, \psi_{g2}, \dots, \psi_{gT})^T$. We assumed a Gaussian Markov Random Field (GMRF) on the latent variables ψ_{git} , which captures the network structure. Let \mathcal{N}_i be the collection of all the index sets of nodes having an edge with node i on network \mathcal{T} , then the network-based GMRF is defined as

$$\psi_{git} \mid \boldsymbol{\psi}_g^{-i}, \mathcal{N}_i \sim N \left(\frac{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \psi_{gjt}}{\#\mathcal{N}_i}, \frac{1}{\#\mathcal{N}_i \tau_g} \right), \quad (6)$$

where $\#\mathcal{N}_i$ is the total number of nodes connected to node i . $\boldsymbol{\psi}_g^{-i}$ is $\boldsymbol{\psi}_g$ but excluding component ψ_{git} from the vector. Equation (6) shows that the expected value of the latent variable in node i is

the average of the values of the latent variables representing the nodes connected to node i , and the variance is scaled by the number of edges of node i . The equation captures the dependency between the nodes across the network. For example consider a network $\mathcal{T} = (\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{E})$ such that the node set is $\mathcal{G} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ and edge set $\mathcal{E} = \{1 \sim 3, 1 \sim 2, 2 \sim 3, 2 \sim 4, 3 \sim 4, 3 \sim 5\}$, where $i \sim j$ indicates that node i is connected to node j on the network. Therefore, $\mathcal{N}_1 = \{2, 3\}$, $\mathcal{N}_2 = \{1, 3, 4\}$, $\mathcal{N}_3 = \{1, 2, 4, 5\}$, $\mathcal{N}_4 = \{2, 3\}$, $\mathcal{N}_5 = \{3\}$. The joint distribution of the network-based-GMRF for the latent variable $\boldsymbol{\psi}_g \mid \boldsymbol{\tau}_g \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\boldsymbol{\tau}_g))$, where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\boldsymbol{\tau}_g) = (\boldsymbol{\tau}_g \mathbf{Q})^{-1}$ and \mathbf{Q} is a structured matrix that captures the spatial structure given in Equation (6), which is defined as

$$Q_{ii'} = \begin{cases} |\mathcal{N}_i|, & \text{if } i = i', \\ -1, & \text{if } j \in \mathcal{N}_i, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

2.2.3 Zero-Inflation joint model

A serious concern with single-cell data is its sparsity. The expression contains excessive zeros that can bias most modeling approaches, especially interpretable models. As a result, it is important to account for these zeroes in the modeling framework to differentiate between true zeroes and biological zeros. To address this concern, we adopted a ‘‘two-part’’ modeling technique. In the first part, we model the activation process of gene g through a logistic model. We model the probability that a specific gene is activated (expressed) or not. In the second step, the extent of activation is modeled through a different standard probability model.

Mathematically, define a new variable Z_{gst} such that

$$Z_{gst} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } Y_{gst} > 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Thus, for a given gene g , we assume that $Z_{gst} \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\pi_{gst})$, where π_{gst} denotes the probability of observing non-zero expression. Moreover, we define another variable $V_{gst} = Y_{gst}$ only if $Z_{gst} = 1$, and V_{gst} is modeled using a zero-truncated negative binomial distribution.

We define ψ_{git} as the latent effect associated with node i at time t . Each spot s is assigned to a node $i(s)$, and thus the spot-level effect is given by $\psi_{gst} = \psi_{g,i(s),t}$. The full model for the SpatialDENet is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
Z_{gst} | \cdot &\sim \text{Bernoulli}(\pi_{gst}), \\
\log\left(\frac{\pi_{gst}}{1 - \pi_{gst}}\right) &= \alpha_{g0} + c_{st}\alpha_{g1} + \mathbf{x}_{st}^T \boldsymbol{\alpha}_g + \psi_{git}, \quad s \in \text{node } i \\
V_{gst} | \cdot &\sim \text{NegativeBinomial}(\mu_{gst}, \phi_g), \\
\log(\mu_{gst}) &= \beta_{g0} + \log(l_{st}) + c_{st}\beta_{g1} + \mathbf{x}_{st}^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_g + \psi_{git}, \quad (9) \\
\boldsymbol{\psi}_g &\sim N(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\tau_g)), \\
(\alpha_{g0}, \alpha_{g1}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_g, \beta_{g0}, \beta_{g1}, \boldsymbol{\beta}_g)^T &\sim \text{MVN}(\mathbf{0}, 10^4 \mathbb{I}), \\
\boldsymbol{\Lambda} &\sim P(\boldsymbol{\Lambda}),
\end{aligned}$$

where π_{gst} is the probability that a specific gene g is biologically activated. Each spot s belongs to a node $i(s)$. Thus, in the linear predictor term, ψ_{git} is included through $\psi_{g,i(s)t}$, which is shared between the binary and the count components. As previously defined, ψ_{git} adjusts for the spatial confounding in the activation component of the model using the network-based-GMRF. $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}$ is a vector of hyperparameters, $\boldsymbol{\Lambda} = (\tau_g, \phi_g)^T$ and $P(\boldsymbol{\Lambda})$ is the prior distribution for $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}$. We assigned log-gamma prior for ϕ_g , $\log(\phi_g) \sim \text{log} - \text{Gamma}(1, 0.00005)$. We adopted the PC prior distribution for τ_g , which is among the most widely used prior distributions due to its robustness. The PC prior distribution for $\tau = \tau_g$ is given as

$$\pi(\tau) = \frac{\lambda}{2} \tau^{-3/2} \exp\left(-\lambda \tau^{-1/2}\right), \quad \text{for } \tau > 0, \quad (10)$$

where $\lambda = -\frac{\log \alpha}{u}$, such that $P(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\tau}} > u) = \alpha$. The prior is fully specified if u and α are fixed or known, which can be informatively derived from the empirical data.

3 Simulation study

We conducted a simulation study to benchmark SpatialDENet with commonly used methods in the literature. To simulate the gene expression data, we adopted a zero inflated negative binomial distribution. To simulate the spatially random error, we adopted a Gaussian bump model. The data generation model is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{xcoord} &\sim \text{uniform}(0, 1) \\
\text{ycoord} &\sim \text{uniform}(0, 1) \\
f_g(s, t) &= \exp\left(-2t((\text{xcoord} - 0.5)^2 + (\text{ycoord} - 0.5)^2)\right) \\
\log(\mu_{gst}) &= \beta_{g0} + c_{st}\beta_{g1} + f_g(s, t) \quad (11) \\
Z_{gst} &\sim \text{Bernoulli}(\pi_{gst}) \\
Y_{gst} &= \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } Z_{gst} = 0, \\ \text{NB}(\mu_{gst}, \phi_g) & \text{if } Z_{gst} = 1. \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

where $xcoord$ and $ycoord$ represent the spatial coordinates of each location, and $f_g(s, t)$ denotes the spatially varying error term, which can potentially confound the estimation of β_{g1} . The error is higher towards the center of the domain and fades away towards the edges. We assumed an effect size of $\beta_{g1} = [2, 4], g = 1, 2, \dots, G$ between the treatment and control conditions. We deliberately introduced this spatial error to evaluate how effectively the network-based model captures spatial structure, without directly simulating from the network-based GMRF.

To simulate the differentially expressed genes, we set $c_{st} = 1$ in the treatment condition and $c_{st} = 0$ in the control condition. To simulate non-differentially expressed genes, we set $\beta_{g1} = 0$ for both treatment and control. In the simulation, $\pi_{gst} = 0.6, \forall g, s, t$. β_0 was fixed to 1 and the dispersion parameter $\tau_g = \phi_g = 1, \forall g$.

Given the simulated data, we compare SpatialDENet with commonly used differential analysis methods in the literature. Specifically, we considered DESeq2³, EdgeR⁴, Limma⁵, MAST⁶, and monocle3¹⁵. Figure 1a shows the randomly selected spatial location with the spatial domain $(0, 1)^2$. Using $f(s, t)$, the figure shows that the spatial pattern exhibits higher intensity moving closer to the center of the spatial domain. This indicates that genes that are more expressed in the center region tend to be relatively more affected by spatial confounding issues. Using the spatial effect $f(s, t)$ in the stochastic representation in Equation (11), differentially and non-differentially expressed genes are simulated. Figure 1b shows the SpatialDENet representation of the spatial domain. Each node is a cluster of neighboring points, and the size of the network determines the number of neighboring spatial locations present in the data. Larger nodes have a higher number of spatial locations. The graph is colored by the node-averaged simulated spatial effect.

Figure 1: Simulation study: (a) The simulated spatial confounding variable distributed across $(0, 1)$ in both x and y axes. (b) The network representation of the simulated spatial region. (c) The power against false discovery rates of the competing models.

We simulated 1000 genes in total. Of those, 100 (10%) differentially expressed genes between control and treatment conditions were simulated. The plot of the power against the false discovery rate between Monocle 3, MAST, DESeq2, EdgeR, and spatialDENet is shown in Figure 1c. The

power and the FDR were computed using

$$\text{Power} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, \text{ FDR} = \frac{FP}{TP + FP}, \quad (12)$$

where TP is true positive, FP is false positive, and FN is false negative. The results showed that DESeq2 achieved a power of 0.80 at an FDR of 0.005, performing relatively well compared to other methods. However, `spatialDENet` outperformed DESeq2, attaining a power of over 0.82 at an FDR of 0.01 and exceeding 0.90 at an FDR of 0.02. In contrast, DESeq2 reached only 0.81 power at the same FDR level of 0.02. These findings highlight the importance of accounting for spatial confounding effects when identifying differentially expressed genes.

We further conducted 30 independent simulation runs to compare `spatialDENet` with other competing models using FDR and power as primary evaluation metrics. For each simulation scenario, we calculated the FDR, power, and the corresponding composite metrics, F1 score, and Youden's J statistic, to assess the overall performance of the models comprehensively. The F1 score and Youden's J statistic are defined as

$$\text{F1} = 2 \frac{(1 - \text{FDR})\text{Power}}{(1 - \text{FDR}) + \text{Power}}, \text{ Youden's J} = \text{Power} - \text{FDR}. \quad (13)$$

Both the F1 score and Youden's J statistic integrate power and FDR to provide a unified measure of a method's true performance. Methods that achieve higher values for these metrics are considered to perform better overall, as they effectively balance sensitivity and false discovery control.

Figure 2: Benchmarking analysis in synthetic data: (a) False discovery rate, (b) Power, (c) unified F1 score, (d) Youden's J statistic.

Figure 2a & b show the box plot of the FDR and power of DESeq2, EdgeR, Limma, MAST, Monocle, and SpatialDENSENet. Findings showed that DESeq2 and SpatialDENSENet had similar levels of FDR, which is better than other competing models. However, judging by the power, SpatialDENSENet outperformed DESeq2 and other competing models (Figure 2b). Moreover, Monocle had the highest

power but with a very high FDR, making it undesirable. Judging by the F1 score and Youden’s J statistic, SpatialDENet outperformed other competing models since it has the highest scores of these unified metrics.

These findings highlight the challenges associated with spatially resolved single-cell differential expression analysis, particularly in datasets affected by complex spatial confounding. Therefore, it is recommended that spatial confounding be accounted for during differential analysis to ensure more accurate and reliable results.

4 Discussion

Differential expression analysis in spatially resolved single-cell data is essential for uncovering localized biological processes and pathways with high spatial precision. While numerous methods exist for identifying differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in conventional single-cell data lacking spatial context, tools tailored for spatially structured data remain limited. A major challenge in spatial DEG analysis is the misalignment between tissue slices under control and perturbed conditions, which renders spatial coordinates incomparable across samples. This issue is further complicated by the inherently cross-sectional (non-longitudinal) design of most spatial transcriptomics experiments. To overcome these limitations, we developed SpatialDENet, a novel framework for identifying DEGs in spatially structured single-cell data. SpatialDENet employs a spatially informed hierarchical model that leverages network-based representations of tissue architecture to account for spatial confounding. This approach offers a powerful and innovative solution for detecting DEGs in misaligned and heterogeneous spatial transcriptomic datasets. We validated SpatialDENet in extensive simulation studies and benchmarked with existing methods, such as DESeq2³, EdgeR⁴, Limma⁵, MAST⁶, and monocle3¹⁵. Judging by the comprehensive F1 score and Youden J statistic, SpatialDENet outperformed other competing methods.

Despite the robustness of SpatialDENet, it has certain limitations. One key challenge lies in selecting the appropriate number of network nodes. While a larger network may yield more precise estimates, it also significantly increases computational time, leading to a trade-off between accuracy and efficiency. Future work could address this issue by incorporating adaptive strategies, such as the elbow method or other optimization algorithms, to automatically determine an optimal network size that balances precision and computational cost. Another limitation is that SpatialDENet estimates the network representation of tissue slices using a deterministic algorithm. Future work can instead consider a probabilistic algorithm to quantify uncertainties regarding edges between nodes.

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